

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 1.7

New near-real time data and time series
from drifting observatories and new
long-term moorings in the interior Arctic

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1 - ESTABLISHING AN ADAPTIVE AND MORE COMPLETE ARCTIC
OBSERVING SYSTEM

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Publishable Executive Summary

The key motivation of the Arctic PASSION project is to contribute to the co-creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system. It aims to overcome known flaws in the present observing system by refining its operability, improving and extending pan-Arctic scientific and community-based monitoring and the integration with Indigenous and Local knowledge. It also aims at streamlining the access and interoperability of Arctic Data systems and services and contribute to ensuring the economic viability and sustainability of the observing system. The main objective of Work Package 1 in the project is to establish the foundation for a comprehensive Arctic observing system of systems (pan-AOSS) that builds on, coordinates and enhances existing observing infrastructures and networks.

This report gives an overview of new observational data from the Arctic Ocean collected with sensors fully or partially funded by the Arctic PASSION project, on drifting sea-ice platforms (“buoys”) and fixed-position (bottom-anchored) deep-ocean moorings. Arctic PASSION has prioritized to 1) expand the long-term mooring-based observations in the Central Arctic Ocean, and 2) sustain, expand and better coordinate European deployments of drifting sea ice buoys in the Eurasian part of the Arctic Ocean. With funding from the project, we have had moorings deployed at new strategic locations throughout the project period and several annual deployments of sea-ice buoys of different types, comprising measurements of key variables of both the sea ice and snow cover, and in the upper part of the water column.

1. Overview of data collecting infrastructures

This report gives an overview of new observational data from the Arctic Ocean collected with sensors fully or partially funded by the Arctic PASSION project, on drifting sea-ice platforms (“buoys”) and fixed-position, bottom-anchored deep-ocean moorings.

1.1 Drifting sea-ice buoys

Drifting sea ice buoys are used to track the evolution of the sea ice cover and its snow in time and space. They are deployed during expeditions and left behind to drift with the sea ice. They report their measurements through satellite communication in near real-time. Hence, this allows monitoring of atmosphere, snow, sea ice, and ocean parameters when manned observations are not possible.

Such buoys come in different forms and levels of complexity. The simplest versions contain only GPS and temperature loggers to track the drift of the ice pack. More complex buoys also report physical properties of snow, sea ice, and ocean. Most sea ice buoys comprise a string of thermistors (temperature sensors) that capture the temporal evolution of temperature through the snow cover and sea ice, and into the underlying water mass. This allows for identification of the snow-sea ice interface and the snow-water interface, as well as capturing episodes of water intrusion and subsequent freezing at the snow-sea ice interface. More advanced drifting platforms comprise sensors measuring properties of the upper part of the water column, either at fixed depths on strings or in profiling units. In this report we provide information on both the basic snow and sea-ice buoys and profiling units that have been deployed with funding and logistics through the Arctic PASSION project.

1.1.1 AWI and NPI buoys

We deployed two types of buoys:

- 1) Sea-ice mass balance buoys: These sea ice buoys comprise a string of thermistors (temperature sensors) that capture the temporal evolution of temperature through the air, snow, and sea ice, and into the underlying water mass. Here we use thermistor string buoys of type SIMBA (SAMS Ice Mass Balance unit; Jackson et al., 2013) (Fig. 1). Data analysis allows the identification of the snow-sea ice and the snow-water interfaces, and thus snow and sea ice thickness over time. In addition, they capture internal snow and sea ice properties, e.g. episodes of water intrusion and subsequent freezing at the snow-sea ice interface.
- 2) Snow Buoys: These sea ice buoys are designed to measure snow depth and air temperature on sea ice (Nicolaus et al., 2021). They are deployed on sea ice and have a mast that holds sensors to measure snow accumulation and ablation (Fig. 2). They are often co-deployed with SIMBA buoys to support snow observations.

AWI and NPI have deployed a total of 32 SIMBA thermistor string buoys (in addition to the nine from CNRS, described in Section 1.1.2, and two from UiT, described in Section 1.1.3) and 23 Snow Buoys with funding contributions from Arctic PASSION, see Table 1 for a summary. The Snow Buoys were, when available, co-deployed with thermistor strings on the same ice floe.

Figure 1. SIMBA thermistor buoy deployed in August 2023. Photo: Mario Hoppmann, AWI.

Figure 2. Snow buoy deployed in August 2023. Photo: Mario Hoppmann, AWI.

Deployments were realized from the following vessels (expeditions):

- FF Kronprins Haakon (2021, 2022 and 2024)
- Polarstern (ATWAICE 2022, ArcWatch-1 2023, and ArcWatch-2 2024)
- KV Svalbard (2024)
- Le Commandant Charcot (2022, 2023, and 2024).

Figure 3 shows the drift tracks of the thermistor string buoys deployed during Arctic PASSION. Snow Buoys, co-deployed with the thermistor strings, drifted along the same trajectory and are not explicitly listed. Metadata and information on co-deployments may be found from the links given in Table 1. The buoys were deployed in the Central Arctic Ocean and drifted towards Fram Strait and the Northern Atlantic Ocean. The trajectories of the buoys deployed during the Polarstern expedition ATWAICE in 2022 were recovered at the end of the expedition and thus have shorter time series. Most buoys deployed in 2024, are still reporting data. With this, Arctic PASSION made a significant contribution to the sea-ice buoy network that was deployed in recent years.

Figure 3. Drift tracks of thermistor string buoys deployed during Arctic PASSION (Status 31 Dec 2024). Deployments from different expeditions are grouped by color for each year. The background shows the sea ice concentration of September 2012, at the summer minimum extent.

1.1.2 CNRS profiler buoys

CNRS has deployed a total of five Ice Atmosphere Ocean Observing System (IAOOS) buoys. IAOOS buoys are ice tethered platforms equipped with a PROVOR SPI ocean profiler (Argo-type) monitoring temperature, salinity and dissolved oxygen by profiling twice a day along a cable in the water column between 5 m and a maximum of 800 m. IAOOS buoys also host a SIMBA ice unit (SAMS Ice Mass Balance, see also Section 1.1.1) monitoring temperature through air, snow, ice and under ice water.

One IAOOS buoy was deployed in September 2021 from RV Kronprins Haakon (NPI cruise) and profiled from 350 m to 5 m; one buoy was planned to be deployed during the GoNorth 2023 NPI cruise from RV Kronprins Haakon but was finally deployed from RV Polarstern (ArcWatch-1 AWI cruise PS138) and profiled from 800 m to 5 m; three platforms were deployed in September 2024 from RV Polarstern (ArcWatch-2 AWI cruise PS144), one profiling from 670 m to 5 m and two profiling from 750 m to 5 m.

A total of nine SIMBA ice buoys from CNRS were deployed over the period 2021-2024 (Fig. 4), five units located together with an IAOOS buoy (see above) and four more apart: one of the latter in 2021 from RV Kronprins Haakon (NPI cruise), two in 2022 from RV Kronprins Haakon (NPI cruise), and one in 2023 from Le Commandant Charcot.

Figure 4. Buoy trajectories from 2021 to November 2024. Color only for SIMBAs, white, and color for full IAOOS buoys.

1.1.3 UiT buoys

UiT deployed a set of six drifters in June 2022 (Fig. 6). The deployment was done during the Arctic Ocean 2022 cruise on RV Kronprins Haakon. The following set of buoys was deployed, close to the North Pole:

- Two SIMBA buoys (further referred to as SIMBA-ITO 02-02 and SIMBA-ITO 02-04, see also Section 1.1.1)
- Two Light and Temperature buoys (LT-ITO "P" 0490 and LT-ITO "Q" 8810) – each consisting of a surface buoy and 50-meter-long chain of sensors attached below. The sensors are grouped in nodes placed 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 9, 14, 21, 32 and 50 m below the surface buoy. Each node contains six light sensors, three of them “looking” upwards and three “looking” downwards. Sensors measure light intensity in “optical counts”, based on which the Photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) can be calculated.
- An Automated Weather Station (AWS-ITO) measuring air temperature, air humidity, atmospheric pressure and wind data.
- A drifter (AZFP-ITO) equipped with an Acoustic Zooplankton and Fish Profiler (AZFP) placed 5 meters below the surface buoy, “looking” downward. The AZFP is an echosounder that operates at 38, 125, 200 and 455 kHz with 1 ms narrow band pulses every 15 seconds. Such a set of frequencies allows for analyzing collected backscatter data both for smaller (plankton) or larger (fish, mammals) organisms.

Figure 5. AZFP-ITO after deployment in June 2022. Photo: Trine Lise Sviggum Helgerud, NPI.

Figure 6. Drift tracks of UiT buoys.

1.2 New moorings in the Central Arctic Ocean

Ocean moorings are bottom-anchored, i.e. fixed-position, installations with sensors that capture time series of selected ocean variables at different depths. In ice-covered waters such moorings are usually deployed with the anchor first and then lowered until they land on the seafloor. The top part of the mooring, supported by buoyancy spheres, typically sits at several tens of meters below the surface, to avoid being caught by the drifting sea ice cover, where ridge keels can extend to depths of 50 meters or more. During recovery of the mooring one must make a sufficiently large hole in the ice cover or wait for an opening, such as a lead, to pass the mooring location.

The moorings deployed with support from the Arctic PASSION project comprise different sensors and time frames (see Fig. 6). Some of the moorings have been intended as new long-term monitoring installations (starting in 2022), while others have been deployed for a limited time (one year) to capture characteristics of key locations from which little previous information on the seasonal cycle exists.

Figure 7. Map showing locations of NPI and AWI moorings, 2022-2024

1.2.1 NPI moorings

In 2022, NPI deployed one mooring in each of the western Nansen and Amundsen Basins of the Central Arctic Ocean (see Fig. 7). Both moorings contain interdisciplinary instrumentation measuring properties of sea ice (drift and draft), physical oceanography (currents, hydrography), biogeochemistry (nitrate, chl a , PAR, automatic water samplers for various laboratory analyses), and biology (sediment traps, passive acoustics for marine mammal detection). The Arctic PASSION project supported instruments for physical oceanography (ADCPs and some CTDs), while other sensors and equipment was funded by other sources.

The two NPI moorings were recovered, serviced and re-deployed in the summer of 2024, with a plan to recover them again in 2026. The data return rate was nearly 100 %.

Figure 8. Deployment of mooring Amundsen-22 in August 2022. Photo: Trine Lise Sviggum Helgerud, NPI.

1.2.2 AWI moorings

Five moorings (“Y1” through “Y5”) were deployed across the Yermak Plateau from July 2022 to June 2023 (see Fig. 7). They were deployed from RV Polarstern on cruise PS131 and recovered from RV Polarstern on cruise PS137 (and a part of Y2 on cruise PS143.2 in 2024). These moorings targeted the upper ocean and the interaction of Atlantic Water with sea ice. As such, the majority of the equipment was deployed as shallow as operationally safe. Y1 and Y2 were in close proximity to each other, but Y2 was equipped with a winch and reached shallower than the fixed-depth sensors of Y1. Similarly, Y3 and Y4 were in close proximity to each other but Y3 had a tube to reach up to 6 m below the surface while Y4 had a biogeochemical cluster at 21 m (McLane RAS, Wetlabs ECO-PAR, Wetlabs ECO-Triplet, Satlantic SUNA, SAMI pH, SAMI pCO₂). The tube was unfortunately lost. Sensors deployed across the array include Seabird SBE37, Seabird SBE37-ODO, Seabird SBE56, RDI Workhorse ADCPs (300kHz and 75kHz), Develogic SonoVault, RBR Wave16, KUM Sediment Trap, WHOI Larvae sampler. The deployment and recovery details of the moorings are shown in Table 2 below.

Two other moorings were deployed in the central, eastern Amundsen Basin at around 4300 m water depth near 85°N, 130°E (Fig. 7). These were deployed in late summer 2023 (cruise PS138) and recovered in late summer 2024 (cruise PS144). with the aim to resolve the seasonal cycle of temperature, salinity and biogeochemistry in the upper, central Arctic Ocean, including the upper mixed layer and the halocline. One mooring was a multidisciplinary, conventional mooring with two biogeochemical clusters (McLane RAS, WETlabs ECO-PAR, Wetlabs ECO-Triplet, Satlantic SUNA, SAMI ph, SAMI pCO₂) and a KUM Sediment Trap, all equipped with Seabird SBE37 / SBE37-ODO. Additional devices include RCM 11, an Aural acoustic recorder, an RDI Workhorse 300 KHz ADCP and a BOP trap. The shallowest devices (the RAS systems) were located between 20 and 30 m depth. The other mooring was a “tube mooring” with an improved design from the one deployed earlier, using a chain instead of a rope at the connecting point between the tube and the lower part of the mooring. The tube reached as shallow as 7 m from the surface, and the mooring was equipped with SBE37 / SBE37-ODO, a Develogic SonoVault, an RDI Longranger 75 KHz ADCP and a Nortek S500 ADCP. The successful recovery in 2024 prompted us to again deploy a tube mooring with a reduced sensor suite (no ADCPs, no deep Seabird SBE37), as the year of recovery is uncertain (potentially 2026).

Figure 9. Recovery of CAO1-01 (“tube”) mooring. Photo: Magnus Lucassen, AWI.

2. Data processing and availability

This section provides brief information on the processing and publication of the buoy and mooring datasets funded by the Arctic PASSION project until summer 2024. Please note that at the time of writing this report, project partners still had active buoys and moorings deployed in the Central Arctic Ocean. Data collected by these installations will be processed and openly shared upon recovery.

2.1 Data from drifting sea ice buoys

2.1.1 AWI and NPI buoys

One aim of the Arctic PASSION work is deriving sea ice thickness, snow depth and sea ice mass balance from the Arctic Ocean. Here we focus on time series data from the buoy. Snow depth may be derived rather straight forward from Snow Buoy measurements, and we continued the work by Nicolaus et al. (2021). The extraction of sea ice thickness data from thermistor string buoys is much more complex and requires intensive data processing. This work was advanced during Arctic PASSION with a publication in progress. Existing publications use individual solutions to derive interface positions between air-snow-sea ice-ocean, which then allows to calculate snow and sea ice thickness. The Arctic PASSION work therefore consisted of the following activities:

1. Collecting data from thermistor string (SIMBA) buoys from 2012 to 2023. A total of 96 buoys were collected. This collection is extended with the 2024 data, work in progress. Raw data sets for each individual buoy were published on PANGAEA,
2. Deriving a processing algorithm to derive interface positions from raw measurements of vertical profiles of temperature and thermal properties of the media,
3. Calculating sea ice and snow thickness as well as interface temperature,
4. Illustrating all data and adding visuals into meereisportal.de
5. Publishing all raw and processed data on PANGAEA as one collection (Preusser et al., 2023) and for each individual buoy.

Based on this work, all buoy data with additional metadata, figures of results and drift trajectories are available from the online sea ice data and information portal www.meereisportal.de (direct link to [data](#)). Final data sets, including the calculation of mass balance parameters, are available on PANGAEA (www.pangaea.de). Individual data sets may be best found by using the Buoy ID (Table 1) as search name. All data are also linked through the “Arctic PASSION” project tag name on PANGAEA.

Table 1: Buoys deployed during the Arctic PASSION project. Names of the buoys indicate the year of deployment, the type of the buoy (S: Snow Buoy, T and M: thermistor buoy), and a counter. The names are consistent with their reference in the data and information portal meereisportal.de, where also all data and metadata may be found (see below). Geographic position is given in decimal degrees. The active period is given as deployment date and date of last data set. If only one date is given, the buoy was still active on 31 December 2024. The download links lead to the data and metadata on the online sea ice data and information portal www.meereisportal.de.

Name	Latitude	Longitude	Active (days)	Link to data
Kronprins Haakon - Nansen Legacy 2021				
2021M31	78.50	-5.99	17.09.21-11.02.22 (146)	Download
Kronprins Haakon – Arctic Ocean 2022				
2022T95	67.74	-27.19	31.07.22-27.02.23 (211)	Download
2022T97	81.29	-3.11	06.08.22-27.12.22 (143)	Download

Le Commandant Charcot - 2022

2022S116	72.83	-13.07	14.07.22-27.01.23 (197)	Download
2022S117	74.55	-10.77	12.08.22-06.02.23 (178)	Download
2022S121	71.99	-8.02	27.08.22-03.03.23 (188)	Download
2022T94	74.68	-10.34	12.08.22-06.02.23 (178)	Download
2022T96	84.49	-4.62	14.07.22-20.01.23 (190)	Download
2022T98	76.86	-7.01	27.08.22-09.02.23 (166)	Download

Polarstern - ATWAICE 2022

2022T91	81.18	2.21	13.07.22-29.07.22 (16)	Download
2022T92	81.08	2.24	15.07.22-31.07.22 (16)	Download
2022T93	80.94	3.88	14.07.22-31.07.22 (17)	Download

Le Commandant Charcot - 2023

2023S126	73.22	-13.80	16.08.23-21.03.24 (218)	Download
2023S128	71.64	-14.99	31.08.23-29.03.24 (210)	Download
2023T111	67.90	-22.65	31.08.23-26.04.24 (239)	Download
2023T112	76.00	-3.06	16.08.23-13.03.24 (210)	Download
2023T113	74.82	-8.89	17.08.23-03.03.24 (200)	Download
2023T114	79.06	-1.42	15.08.23-09.02.24 (178)	Download

Polarstern ArcWatch-1 2023

2023T103	80.00	7.53	30.08.23 (still active)	Download
2023S100	75.77	-8.46	09.09.23-27.02.24 (170)	Download
2023S101	78.08	-2.59	13.09.23-11.03.24 (180)	Download
2023S102	76.26	-8.38	04.09.23-19.04.24 (228)	Download
2023S103	80.80	25.41	10.08.23-25.12.23 (137)	Download
2023S122	84.27	110.69	01.09.23-28.08.24 (362)	Download
2023S123	84.93	72.82	25.08.23-25.08.24 (366)	Download
2023S124	86.18	45.82	30.08.23-17.05.24 (261)	Download
2023S125	84.95	46.78	30.08.23-25.08.24 (361)	Download
2023S127	85.03	42.18	28.08.23-17.08.24 (355)	Download
2023T99	86.62	121.02	25.08.23-07.03.24 (195)	Download
2023T100	77.53	-2.44	13.09.23-15.03.24 (184)	Download
2023T102	75.92	-7.91	04.09.23-20.04.24 (229)	Download
2023T104	81.47	24.75	09.08.23-08.12.23 (121)	Download
2023T105	84.69	36.73	01.09.23-10.08.24 (345)	Download
2023T106	85.01	40.11	28.08.23-13.08.24 (351)	Download
2023T107	62.19	-37.41	03.09.23-09.09.24 (372)	Download
2023T109	85.15	24.56	29.08.23-19.06.24 (294)	Download
2023T110	74.19	-8.54	10.09.23-13.03.24 (186)	Download

Le Commandant Charcot - 2024

2024S139	89.19	-148.52	13.09.24 (still active)	Download
2024S140	85.51	-20.52	16.09.24 (still active)	Download
2024T123	85.52	-20.45	15.09.24 (still active)	Download

Polarstern - ArcWatch-2 2024

2024S129	88.09	81.18	30.08.24 (still active)	Download
2024S130	89.03	-178.81	05.09.24 (still active)	Download
2024S131	87.42	-155.84	08.09.24 (still active)	Download

<u>2024S132</u>	86.19	-144.53	11.09.24 (still active)	<u>Download</u>
<u>2024S136</u>	88.28	-81.72	13.09.24 (still active)	<u>Download</u>
<u>2024S137</u>	84.48	-0.28	25.09.24 (still active)	<u>Download</u>
<u>2024S138</u>	84.57	-7.52	23.09.24 (still active)	<u>Download</u>
<u>2024T101</u>	84.48	-0.23	25.09.24 (still active)	<u>Download</u>
<u>2024T108</u>	87.42	-155.84	05.09.24 (still active)	<u>Download</u>
<u>2024T116</u>	87.42	-155.84	08.09.24 (still active)	<u>Download</u>
<u>2024T117</u>	86.19	-144.35	11.09.24 (still active)	<u>Download</u>
<u>2024T118</u>	84.56	-7.59	23.09.24 (still active)	<u>Download</u>
<i>Kronprins Haakon - NPI AO2024</i>				
<u>2024T126</u>	72.34	-15.52	31.07.24 (still active)	<u>Download</u>
<u>2024T127</u>	75.38	-12.67	26.07.24 (still active)	<u>Download</u>
<u>2024T128</u>	68.58	-23.55	27.07.24 (still active)	<u>Download</u>

Figures 10 and 11 show an example result for buoy 2019T72. This buoy was deployed during the MOSAiC drift experiment in 2019-2020 (Nicolaus et al., 2022). This example is taken from a publication in progress showing the data processing method, including the discussion of challenges and uncertainties (tentative title: Preusser et al.: Lagrangian time series of sea ice thickness, snow depth and interface temperatures as derived from sea ice mass balance buoy data for 2012-2024). These analyses were performed for all existing buoy data sets (96 completed, more in progress). They are the basis for further analyses of sea ice processed in the Arctic. Additional work, not included here, also considers the same analyses for sea ice in the Antarctic, where mass balance studies are also based on SIMBA buoy measurements.

Figure 10 shows the raw data as measured from the thermistor string, as shown on meereisportal.de. The panels give the temperatures measured for each thermistor (top), the heating mode temperature after 30s (middle), and the heating mode temperature after 120s (bottom). Gradients in these data indicate transition of media, which is the main aspect to derive interfaces.

Figure 10: Raw data from thermistor string buoy 2019T72, which was deployed on sea ice during the MOSAiC expedition. The figure is taken from meereisportal.de (link see Table 1).

Figure 11 shows the resulting snow and sea ice thickness for buoy 2019T72 (top panel). In order to derive these mass balance parameters, the other panels shown in Figure 6 are used. The calculation of the environmental temperature from the thermistors in air, the environmental temperature gradient and thermal proxies are used to visualize interfaces of the different media. The method uses differences of thermal properties in the different media (air, snow, sea ice, sea water).

Results from Figure 11 show an increase of sea ice thickness from 0.90 to 2.20 m over the Arctic winter from 9 October 2019 to 28 April 2020. Snow thickness was rather constant around 0.20 m for most of the

time, until new snowfall (starting 8 April) accumulated an additional 0.10 m in spring. The additional snow increased thermal insulation against the air, causing increased sea ice temperatures.

Overall, the progress on analyzing SIMBA type sea ice mass balance buoy data allows a generalization of mass balance studies in the Arctic Ocean. The data collection across different previous projects and various international partners since 2012 combines all available information into a common system, which goes beyond Arctic PASSION and its partners. The existing data processing system may be applied to ongoing and future data sets. It requires manual interaction, but also reduces the dependencies on individual approaches and interpretations.

Figure 11: Processed data from thermistor string buoy 2019T72, deployed on sea ice during the MOSAiC expedition. (a) Snow thickness and sea ice thickness with uncertainties (shaded areas). (b) Environmental temperature (proxy for air temperature), mostly used to derive the air-snow interface. (c) Thermal proxy derived from the heating temperatures, mostly used to derive the ice-ocean interface. (d) Vertical gradient of environmental temperature, mostly used to derive the snow-ice interface. Dashed white lines give the derived interfaces, which are the basis for the snow and sea ice thickness calculation in panel (a).

2.1.2 CNRS profiler buoys

Table 2 gives an overview of the data sets collected during buoy deployments by CNRS. This data has not been published yet.

Table 2. CNRS buoy ID, deployment date (UTC) and position (in decimal degrees), and URL for data.

Buoy #	Deployment date	Deployment position (Lat/Lon)	Data availability
31: ice/ocean	12-Sep-2021 14:00	86.39 / -16.66	Not published yet
32: ice	17-Sep-2021 19:00	87.49 / -18.41	Not published yet
33: ice	02-Aug-2022 14:00	87.10 / -41.13	Not published yet
34: ice	04-Aug-2022 21:00	87.66 / -33.53	Not published yet
35: ice	01-Sep-2023 14:00	87.09 / 32.33	Not published yet
36: ice/ocean	09-Sep-2023 10:00	89.93 / 8.49	Not published yet
37: ice/ocean	28-Aug-2024 07:59	84.28 / 110.83	Not published yet
38: ice/ocean	14-Sep-2024 10:00	87.44 / 177.68	Not published yet
39: ice/ocean	19-Sep-2024 10:59	89.95 / -143.47	Not published yet

2.1.3 UiT buoy cluster

Table 3. Deployment date (UTC) and position (in decimal degrees), and dates with positions of last received report.

Unit	Deployment date	Deployment position (Lat/Lon)	Date of last message	Last reported position (Lat/Lon)
AWS-ITO	2022-07-29	89.82 / -26.28	2023-01-20	73.43 / -13.90
AZFP-ITO	2022-07-29	89.82 / -26.28	2023-10-11	59.76 / -48.67
LT-ITO "P" 0490	2022-07-31	89.72 / -28.28	2022-10-19	85.69 / 3.54
LT-ITO "Q" 8810	2022-07-31	89.73 / -28.20	2022-10-19	85.70 / 3.56
SIMBA-ITO 02-04	2022-07-29	89.85 / -29.11	2023-01-30	71.55 / -14.34
SIMBA-ITO 02-02	2022-07-29	89.85 / -29.42	2023-02-01	71.04 / -14.88

Table 4. Data collection summary

Unit	Collected data	Date of last datapoint
AWS-ITO	Air temperature, air humidity and atmospheric pressure were collected for almost half year. Presumably due to the icing the correct wind measurements could not be obtained for most of the drift time.	2023-01-20
AZFP-ITO	Positions and diagnostic messages are being sent via satellite communication. Actual data volume from that instrument is too high to be sent that way. Data were downloaded via Maritime Broadband radio link from Luftransport Dornier228 plane. Data download flights were conducted twice, on 2022-11-17 and 2023-01-18.	2023-01-18
LT-ITO "P" 0490	Light data were sent via satellite communication and were successfully collected till unit 's batteries were depleted in mid October 2022.	2022-10-19
LT-ITO "Q" 8810	Light data were sent via satellite communication and were successfully collected till unit 's batteries were depleted in mid October 2022.	2022-10-19
SIMBA-ITO 02-04	The unit was sending ice data for two weeks. Most likely the sensor chain was physically damaged after that time. The ITO continued sending status messages and GPS positions till the end of January.	2022-08-14
SIMBA-ITO 02-02	About two months of ice data were collected (data received via satellite communication). Presumably due to antenna icing data transmission stopped in late September. Unit resumed sending data in the beginning of January and continued till Jan 19. In the beginning of February all communication stopped.	Data was received for two time periods: 2022-07-29 to 2022-09-26 2023-01-01 to 2023-01-27

Data processing pipeline

Data from the majority of the UiT drifters (all except the AZFP-ITO, which had their data downloaded via radio from aircraft, see table 4) were sent by Iridium SDB messages (Figure 12). The messages were received in form of email attachments and handled by an hourly-ran routine. The incoming messages were consolidated to one object (text or binary file, depending on the data format specific for particular drifter). When necessary, messages were decoded (data sent from LT-ITO and AWS-ITO were encoded for economic use of Iridium messages). The data were afterwards compiled to tabular format and stored as Pandas pickle file, for efficient and quick access. Data in this format were used for analysis and plotting. The last stage of processing was to combine the data with metadata and to save them as CF-NetCDF files.

Figure 12. General data processing pipeline

Table 5. Information on data publication including dois. The joint “parent” data set has doi <https://doi.org/10.21343/wj48-y250>

Unit	Data published	Data format	doi
AWS-ITO	Air temperature, air humidity and atmospheric pressure.	NetCDF-CF	https://doi.org/10.21343/05e0-m202
AZFP-ITO	Bioacoustics data from an Acoustic Zooplankton and Fish Profiler (AZFP) GPS track of the drift.	Echosounder data in AZFP format * NetCDF + csv	https://doi.org/10.21343/dbbr-w495
LT-ITO "P" 0490	Upwelling and downwelling visible radiation measurements	Tab-delimited text	https://doi.org/10.21343/kzp6-aq05
LT-ITO "Q" 8810	Upwelling and downwelling visible radiation measurements	Tab-delimited text	https://doi.org/10.21343/kzp6-aq05 (same as above - joint data set)
SIMBA-ITO 02-04	No usable ice data was collected.	-	-
SIMBA-ITO 02-02	Ice data (temperatures and temperature deltas from heating cycles) for periods when data was received: 2022-07-29 to 2022-09-26 and 2023-01-01 to 2023-01-27.	Tab-delimited text	https://doi.org/10.21343/kbbt-8s15

* note: the AZFP data are being reprocessed to be machine readable, and hence not available in such format at the time of submitting the report.

2.2 Data from new moorings in the Central Arctic Ocean

This section provides brief information on the processing and publication of mooring data funded by the Arctic PASSION project until summer 2024. Please note that at the time of writing this report, project partners NPI and AWI still had moorings deployed in the Central Arctic Ocean. Data collected by these installations will be processed and openly shared upon recovery.

2.2.1 NPI moorings

Here we describe data from physical oceanography (PO) instruments funded by the Arctic PASSION project. Data from all other sensors on the moorings will be published in the same open access data base but since processing of biogeochemical and biological data is more cumbersome than that of standard PO data, remaining data will be published sequentially in 2025 and 2026.

Hydrographic time series data were collected using temperature (T) and conductivity-temperature-depth (CTD) instruments mounted along the two mooring lines. Data from these instruments are processed, quality-controlled and formatted for publication using the Python oceanographic processing module *kval* (github.com/NPIOcean/kval) which is under development at NPI.

Ocean current data were collected using a dual set of Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCP) on each mooring. Data from these instruments are converted to physical units using manufacturer software and subsequently undergo basic post-processing, quality flagging and formatting in Python.

Processed time series data in NetCDF format are supplied for each individual instrument. Raw data are made available alongside processed time series.

Table 6. Deployment and recovery information for NPI's new moorings in the central Arctic Ocean.

	Amundsen-22	Nansen-22
Latitude	86°31.582' N (86.53 °N)	83°56.566' N (83.94 °N)
Longitude	5°36.575' W (5.61 °W)	22°15'038 E (22.25 °E)
Bottom depth	4215 m	4025 m
Deployment period	07.08.2022 – 30.07.2024	15.08.22 - 06.08.24
Data DOI/URL	doi.org/10.21334/npolar.2024.92445174	doi.org/10.21334/npolar.2024.67ffb476

2.2.2 AWI moorings

The processing of the physical sensors on the AWI moorings was done in accordance with the standard AWI mooring processing routine as laid out in this technical report: <https://epic.awi.de/id/eprint/43137/>. The biogeochemical sensors were processed in a similar manner to exclude times of non-deployment and blowdown. Comparison to CTD bottle data on the deployment and recovery cruises was used for calibration purposes.

Data and instruments of the moorings recovered in the Central Arctic Ocean in late summer 2024 were still being processed and calibrated at the time of this report, and the corresponding expedition report is still in preparation.

Table 7. Names, positions (decimal degrees), deployment and recovery dates (UTC), water depth for Yermak Plateau moorings.

Name	Latitude	Longitude	Deployed [date]	Recovered [date]	Water depth [m]
Y1-1	80.40	10.06	July 18 2022	June 25 2023	689
Y2-1	80.42	10.06	July 18 2022	June 25 2023	677
Y3-1	80.95	8.72	July 19 2022	June 26 2023	760
Y4-1	80.97	8.70	July 19 2022	June 26 2023	774
Y5-1	81.50	7.15	July 20 2022	June 27 2023	477

DOIs with URLs for the Y-moorings 2022-2023:

Y1-1: <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.974309>

Y2-1: <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.974312>

Y3-1: <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.974314>

Y4-1: <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.974317>

Y5-1: <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.974316>